

Origin of Oscillations in Bound State Quantum Mechanics?

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It seems a signature feature of quantum bound state is the presence of oscillations. For example, in an oscillator, these are present both in $P(x)$ and $P(p)$ for states above the ground state. In addition, they do not disappear even as one approaches a high energy eigenvalue limit. The correspondence principle applies to an envelope of the density $W(x)W(x)$ ($W(x)$ =wavefunction), but oscillations still remain. They are also present for a particle in a box without a potential. In this note, we try to examine how these oscillations of a single particle can lead to more complicated oscillations for a particle in a potential.

Single Particle

The quantum mechanical single particle is modeled by $W(x) = \exp(ikx - Et)$ which is mathematically a wave type motion. Nevertheless, the density is $1 (W(x)^*W(x))$, the momentum density $k (W^* k W)$ and the kinetic energy density $(W^* \hbar k/2m W) \hbar k/2m$. All of these density values match classical values. It is only when one has interference that some interesting quantum mechanical features appear. This interference seems to be related to correlations as well. Consider a particle in a box which classically bounces back and forth. Quantum mechanically one expects a similar process and so writes $\exp(ikx - Et)$ and $\exp(+ikx - Et)$ for forward and backward waves. This raises the question of a relative phase between the two. In quantum mechanics only a phase of 0 or π lead to resonances (or appropriate multiples) leading to the notion of correlation between the forward and backward wave. This seems to suggest a physical inner motion in a quantum particle (1) which imposes constraints on the reflection which occurs at a wall. This seems to be similar to a photon reflecting in classical electromagnetism. In addition to the correlation, there appears to be interference as the complex $\exp(ikx - Et)$ and $\exp(-ikx - Et)$ may combine to create a purely real or complex result e.g. $\cos(kx)$. This is not just a mathematical curiosity, it leads to consequences for the density $W(x)W(x)$ which are completely unclassical, unlike in the case of a quantum particle moving to the right or to the left. One may see $\cos(kx)$ is a periodic function, thus there is not only correlation and interference, but also periodicity. It may be noted that $\cos(kx)$ is only one of many types of periodic functions. A question that arises is whether the periodicity present in a quantum particle in a box has any direct consequences on a larger scale periodicity which may exist for a particle in a potential.

Quantum Particle in a Potential

The single particle in a box leads to the notion of correlation, interference and periodicity. It is possible this may carry over to a quantum particle in a potential. Consider such a particle scattering from one state $\exp(-ikx - Et)$ to another. In general, these different states could have

different weights and phases, but this does not occur. Single particle states seem to be correlated (i.e. have either 0 or π as their phase) and the same weight or magnitude of weight. (Note: A Fourier series for an even $W(x)$ is based on $\cos(kx)$ and for an odd, on $\sin(kx)$.) They also interfere. Thus, one may suggest there is a long time average of single particle kinetic energy governed by these constraints:

$$\left[\sum_{\text{over } p} p^2/2m \int p \exp(ipx) \right] / W(x) = C \left[\sum_{\text{over } p} p^2/2m \cos(px) \right] / W(x) = .5 m v(x)v(x) \quad ((1))$$

$$(-1/2m) \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x) / W(x) = .5 m v(x)v(x)$$

Here we have chosen even symmetry (i.e. $\cos(kx)$) and suggest this average single particle kinetic energy equals classical kinetic energy at each point. Here $W(x) = \sum_{\text{over } p} \int p \exp(ipx)$ and serves as a normalization constant in ((1)). Thus, one seems to be dealing with conditional probabilities, namely $P(p/x)$. The normalization function $W(x)$ (which is called the wavefunction) is a function of x precisely because one is using $\exp(ipx)$, the single particle wavefunction. Thus, consequences due to the space dependence of W follow in a sense from the single particle form. An immediate consequence is that mathematically $W(x)$ may be 0. Given the $v(x)$ does not vanish at any x point (except at end points), the numerator and denominator of ((1)) must both approach 0. One can then apply l'Hopital's rule to find:

$$(-1/2m) \frac{(d/dx)^3 W(x_0)}{d/dx W(x_0)} > 0 \text{ for } W(x_0)=0 \quad ((2))$$

This implies $d/dx W(x_0)$, the derivative of $W(x)$ evaluated at x_0 is nonzero. This derivative is associated with changes in density, namely:

$$d/dx [W(x)W(x)] = 2 W(x) d/dx W(x) \text{ to first order} \quad ((3))$$

Even when $W(x_0)=0$, the density is changing at this point and so $d/dx W(x_0) > 0$ or < 0 is not unreasonable. It should be noted that ((2)) is also related to the Schrodinger equation:

$$(-1/2m) \left\{ (1/W) (d/dx)^3 W(x) - (1/W^*W) d/dx d/dx W \right\} = -d/dx V(x) \quad ((4))$$

One may multiply by $W(x)$ and then evaluate at $x=x_0$:

$$(-1/2m) (d/dx)^3 W(x) = .5 m v(x)v(x) \text{ at } x= x_0 \quad ((5))$$

It should be noted that since one is using conditional probabilities, an average p at a point x may be defined by:

$$(1/W(x)) d/dx W(x) = (1/W(x)) \sum_{\text{over } p} p \int p \exp(ipx) \quad ((6))$$

Here again $W(x)$ is a normalization constant. At $x=x_0$, ((6)) is singular, but if one multiplies by $W(x)W(x)$ everything is fine. Thus, the velocity defined by ((6)) makes sense only when taken in context with density. It does not stand as a velocity by itself as $(-1/2m) (1/W) d/dx d/dx W$ represents $.5 m v(x)v(x)$ everywhere. This also seems to be important in trying to understand quantum bound states.

Given that $W(x_0)=0$, there may be other points where this holds, namely $W(x_i)=0$ for certain x_i . This leads to the notion of a kind of periodic wavefunction in a potential, which in turn leads to a periodic density $W(x)W(x)$ i.e. one that resembles a standing wave. At x_i one may think in terms of linear algebra i.e.

Sum over $p \{ f_p \} \{ \exp(ip x_i) \} = 0$ where f_p is a row vector of weights and $\exp(ip x_i)$ a column vector. ((7)).

Thus, the single particle states $\exp(ipx)$ change values throughout space, but at certain x_i points form vectors which are perpendicular to the weight vector. It also follows that:

$$\text{Sum over } p \{ p^* p f_p \} \{ \exp(ip x_i) \} = 0 \quad ((8))$$

Thus, single particle states are like dimensions of a vector. Each dimension is periodic i.e. $\exp(ipx)$, but the whole vector is also periodic becoming orthogonal to the vector $\{ f_p \}$ at certain x_i .

Similarly, one may show from the Schrodinger equation that:

$$\text{Sum over } k \{ V_k f_{p-k} \} = (E - p^2/2m) f_p \quad ((9))$$

Taking the dot product of both sides of ((9)) with $\{ \exp(ipx) \}$ (summing over p) gives a right hand side with two terms which are both zero. For the left hand side:

$$\text{Sum over } k, p \{ V_k \exp(+ikx) \exp(-ikx) f_{p-k} \} = \text{Sum over } k \{ V_k \exp(ikx) \} \text{Sum over } p \{ f_{p-k} \exp(i(p-k)x) \}$$

$$\text{With } \text{Sum over } p \{ f_{p-k} \exp(i(p-k)x) \} = 0.$$

In addition, the vector $\{ f_{p-k} \}$ may be orthogonal to V_k (the Fourier transform of $V(x)$) leading to $f_p=0$. Thus, one may have periodicity in both $W(x)$ and f_p . $\{ f_{p-k} \}$ is a permuted vector of f_p 's. Thus, one has permutations of the f_p vector which combine with V_k to form each f_p . For some cases, f_p becomes 0. This has the appearance of a periodic disturbance in f_p space.

Conclusion: Consequences of Periodicity

It may at first seem that periodicity present in quantum bound states is simply a curiosity. It seems, however, that not only does one have the form of standing waves, but that there is a

specific periodic motion occurring. As noted, in space one has the vector $\{\exp(ipx)\}$ which changes from one x to another, but becomes perpendicular to the vector $\{fp\}$ at certain x_i points. For fp , the vector $\{fp-k\}$ changes as one permutes fp 's to create different fp values in ((9)). For certain permutations, this vector becomes perpendicular of the vector $\{Vk\}$ and one has $fp=0$. Thus, there seems to be a physical periodicity occurring in quantum bound states (both in space and momentum space) albeit a strange one. It is suggested this periodicity may be directly related to the idea that sound waves may be absorbed and emitted from qubit systems as there seems to be a physical periodicity in quantum mechanics.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. 2x2 Matrix Model and the Schrodinger Equation (preprint, zenodo, 2018)